

naphthazarin and quinizarin have been reported. An attempt in this direction may throw light on the selective absorption and transport mechanism of alkaline earth metal cations from soil to plants.

The present investigation examines the properties of 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone (H_2BQ), naphthazarin (H_2NZ) and quinizarin (H_2BZ) towards alkaline earth metal salts and to compare them with the previously investigated properties of transition metal chelates of 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone and naphthazarin (5,8-dihydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone)²⁻⁴.

Experimental

Preparation of ligand: 2,5-Dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone⁵ and naphthazarin⁶ were prepared by reported methods. Quinizarin (AnalaR) ir spectra was used as such.

Preparation of complexes $MBQ \cdot 2H_2O$ ($M=Mg, Ca, Sr$ or Ba): To a solution of alkaline earth metal acetate (0.3 g) dissolved in 95% ethanol was added excess of ligand (H_2BQ) and a clear solution was obtained. It was refluxed on a hot-plate with continuous stirring for 15 min to 2 h and the resulting solid was washed with 95% ethanol and dried at 100°. The same procedure was followed for the preparation of $MNZ \cdot 2H_2O$ ($M=Mg$ or Ca) and MNZ ($M=Sr$ or Ba), and $MQZ \cdot 2H_2O$ ($M=Mg$ or Ca) and MQZ ($M=Sr$ or Ba).

Results and Discussion

The complexes of alkaline earth metal acetate are coloured. Generally these complexes are slightly soluble in organic solvents like ethanol, acetone and methanol, but they are soluble in DMF. This indicates the complexes are polymeric in nature. The complexes are stable and show no change even after a long period. All the complexes (Table 1) either decompose or undergo a transformation at temperature which are considerably higher than the melting point of the corresponding ligand, indicating their greater thermal stability.

The ir spectra of dihydroxybenzoquinone showed a sharp peak at 3300 cm^{-1} (OH) which shifted slightly in the spectra of the chelates and is much broader, perhaps due to the water molecule present in them. On this basis it can be concluded that the phenolic hydrogen present in H_2BQ were released in the formation of the complexes. This is supported by the absence of the three ir ligand bands in the 1200 cm^{-1} , in the metal complexes. This is a region that is normally assigned to the OH bending vibration. The rocking δ_{H_2O} has also been spotted at $850-840\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for all the complexes. The strong hydrogen bonded carbonyl absorption at 1618 cm^{-1} shifted below 1600 cm^{-1} . This assignment has also been confirmed earlier³ for transition metal complexes.

Alkaline Earth Metal Chelate Polymers with Naturally occurring Substrate

D. PRAKASH*, R. N. SINGH, R. L. VERMA

and

OM PRAKASH GUPTA

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-800 005

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IN recent years, much interest exists in the poly-nuclear complexes, which can hold metal centers in close proximity. The hydroxyquinones are of practical interest¹ on account of their occurrence in nature, their extensive use in technology as mordant dyes and dye intermediates. It appears from the literature survey that no chelate polymers of alkaline earth metals with 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone,

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	M.p./ decomp. temp. (°C)	Analysis (%): Found/(Calcd.)		
			C	H	Metal
H ₂ BQ	Orange yellow	198m	51.41 (51.43)	2.85 (2.86)	—
MgBQ.2H ₂ O	Pink	280d	35.80 (36.36)	3.20 (3.03)	12.00 (12.12)
CaBQ.2H ₂ O	Pink	275d	33.80 (33.64)	2.85 (2.80)	18.50 (18.69)
SrBQ.2H ₂ O	Light pink	285d	25.85 (27.48)	2.32 (2.29)	32.90 (33.58)
BaBQ.2H ₂ O	Pink	270d	24.50 (23.15)	2.10 (1.92)	42.85 (44.05)
H ₂ NZ	Blackish brown	192m	63.10 (63.16)	3.12 (3.16)	—
MgNZ.2H ₂ O	Blue violet	320d	46.90 (48.38)	3.25 (3.22)	9.50 (9.67)
CaNZ.2H ₂ O	Purple	310d	44.80 (45.45)	3.10 (3.03)	15.00 (15.15)
SrNZ	Purple	300d	43.20 (43.47)	1.48 (1.44)	30.75 (31.88)
BaNZ	Purple	295d	36.25 (36.92)	1.25 (1.23)	41.50 (42.15)
H ₂ QZ	Dark red	198m	—	—	—
MgQZ.2H ₂ O	Deep purple	>320	56.30 (56.37)	3.36 (3.35)	7.95 (8.05)
CaQZ.2H ₂ O	Purple	>320	53.30 (53.50)	3.15 (3.18)	12.70 (12.73)
SrQZ	Flash	>320	51.20 (51.53)	1.86 (1.84)	26.00 (26.95)
BaQZ	Violet	>320	43.95 (44.80)	1.65 (1.60)	35.80 (36.53)

H₂NZ and H₂QZ contain intra-molecular hydrogen bonding⁷. The spectra of the metal complexes of H₂NZ and H₂QZ did not reveal OH absorption except in the magnesium and calcium complexes because hydrogen atoms of phenolic group has been replaced by alkaline earth metal. In the magnesium and calcium complexes, two water molecules are coordinated which are lost at ~140°, showing strong association. Broad OH absorption was observed at 3 300 and 3 350 cm⁻¹ for the Mg and Ca complexes respectively. The rocking δ_{H₂O} band was found at 850 cm⁻¹ for the magnesium and 840 cm⁻¹ for the calcium complexes.

The hydrogen bonded C=O band at 1 621 cm⁻¹ in H₂NZ and at 1 635 cm⁻¹ in H₂QZ is shifted by 25–70 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of their alkaline earth metal chelates. If the alkaline earth metal chelates of H₂BQ, H₂NZ and H₂QZ had a purely ionic structure, the carbonyl peak in these compounds would have been observed at a higher frequency very near to that of free ketone of quinone (1 690–1 660 cm⁻¹), instead, the absorption occurs at 1 610–1 550 cm⁻¹. The close similarity of the spectra of the complexes of H₂BQ, H₂NZ and H₂QZ to those of the transition metal acetylacetonate⁸ clearly indicates that these are chelated compounds.

The studies suggest the coordination of alkaline earth metal with 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone, naphthazarine and quinizarin through oxygen atom of the phenolic group as well as through oxygen atom of quinone group. Moreover, H₂BQ, H₂NZ

and H₂QZ behave as a double-faced bidentate ligand in these complexes.

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